

American Geophysical Union Fall Meeting December 12th, 2022

GH15A-07 - Assessment of the Gulf Coast Environmental Justice Landscape for Equity (AGEJL-4-Equity)

Abstract

Environmental damage and climate change related hazards are unequally distributed in communities on Earth in patterns that are often observable from space. Since the earliest investigations of the disproportionate burden of environmental ills sited in marginalized and disempowered communities, it has been clear that EJ community context, stakeholders, issues and drivers differ from one region to another. The purpose of the AGEJL-4-Equity project is to improved capabilities and recognition of EJ community members to use Earth science, including NASA open science, as an evidence base to frame EEJ decision making and solutions in an inclusive and scientifically valid way. Comparative analysis helps to appreciate this important diversity of experience to highlight evidence gaps such as the intersection of hurricane vulnerability and point source pollution on the Gulf Coast. Using participatory mapping tools developed and supported with a common multi-disciplinary multi-perspective EEJ analytical frame, four Equity and Environmental Justice (EEJ) networks convened to map Southern Gulf Coast, primarily African American, underserved EJ communities and their priorities: the National Black Environmental Justice Network, the Historically Black College and University-Community Based Organization Gulf Coast Equity Consortium, the Deep South Center for Environmental Justice (DSCEJ) Community Advisory Board, and the Environmental Justice Forum. The EEJ networks received capacity development-centered support through an Earth science-focused adaptation of the tried-and-true Communiversality participatory assessment model. Together, the project mapped underserved EEJ stakeholder communities, EEJ priorities, ways of working, and knowledge of Earth science-based evidence to advance EEJ decision-making and action presented in a comprehensive network-landscape analysis.